

NEW EDUCATION REFORMS IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: *Modern life today is unimaginable without the advancement of science and education, as if humanity were revolving around the axis of science. It is no coincidence that the development of education is a priority in the world's leading countries. After all, the future development of the country is closely linked with its achievements in this area. This article discusses reforms in education in recent years.*

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We all know that the cornerstone of development, as well as the power that makes a country strong and a nation great, is science, education and upbringing. Our future, the bright future of our Motherland, is closely linked, first of all, with the education system and the upbringing of our children.

Shavkat Mirziyoev

Today, all spheres of life in New Uzbekistan have become a platform for profound reforms. In this process, it is impossible not to talk excitedly about the changes in the education system, which are the basis of the social sphere. Further development of the education system in our country, in particular, the system of public education, which is the main and decisive link in education, to bring it to a new level, to encourage the work of coaches and educators, to support them in all respects, education, science and Integrated development of the cultural sphere and their continuous improvement have been identified as the main and priority directions of the state policy. In his Address to the Oliy Majlis and the people, of course, special attention should be paid to the field of education, and in the words of the President: We have set ourselves the main goal of creating the foundations of the Fourth Renaissance.

As a result of the political will and efforts of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev, the problems accumulated over the years in the education system have been gradually resolved over the past four years. , reduction of paperwork in the work of teachers, simplification of

their qualification, improvement of professional development of teachers, the opening of specialized, creative and Presidential schools, the establishment of integrated cooperation between higher education and secondary schools, increasing quotas for admission to higher education institutions. The system of remuneration of coaches has been improved, their salaries have been significantly increased, and as a result of these changes and conditions, secondary schools have been relocated. The return of teachers, the change in the quality of education from quantity to quality, the expansion of the ranks of our youth among the winners of international science Olympiads, all this is directly related to the personality and activities of our President Shavkat Mirziyoev. In particular, one of the most important documents adopted in the education system was the adoption of a new version of the Law on Education. According to this law, the basic principles, system, types and forms of education are clearly defined. In particular, the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 serves as a prelude to new reforms in this area.

The document is based on such tasks as the acceleration of intellectual development, training of competitive personnel, effective organization of scientific and innovative activities and the development of integration of science, education and industry in order to strengthen international cooperation. The content of the concept reflects the priorities of reforming the higher education system of the country. It outlines areas for expanding university coverage and improving the quality of education, the introduction of digital technologies and educational platforms, the involvement of young people in research, the formation of innovative structures, the commercialization of research results, international recognition and many more. All this serves to raise the educational process to a new level of quality. Non-governmental higher education institutions are being established on the basis of a public-private partnership system. After studying the opinion of the population, part-time and evening education has been restored, and admission quotas have been increased. The enrollment rate of graduates in higher education increased from 9% in 2016 to 25% in 2020. The increase in the number of state grants for higher education by at least 25 percent, and the doubling of the number of grants for girls from needy families to higher education to 2,000, further expanded the scope of higher education enrollment.

In conclusion, reforms in the field of education today are no less relevant and practical than reforms in other areas. This is because it is time to continue reforms in this area on a larger scale

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